

IN STUDENTS VOCAL CHOIR QUALIFICATIONS OF FORMATION NEW
EDITORIAL TECHNOLOGY AND METHODS

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Abstract: Article in students vocals - chorus qualifications to form dedicated. In it to sing of qualifications theoretical basics with get to know one in line education in the process general didactic and special music of pedagogy main principles and their content - essence to students absorb

Key's words: music, culture, choir, vocal , skill, technology, method, editor.

The term educational technology is based on a new, systematic approach to the educational process, which has its own characteristics and features. This means an innovative approach to the educational process. The organization of new education means bringing into the educational process advanced methods and techniques used in the practice of world pedagogy, technical means, forms of teaching, taking into account the personality, spiritual identity, intellectual capabilities, national and social characteristics of each student. The new educational technology requires students to be viewed as subjects of the educational process, that is, as active participants, and the teacher as the organizer and manager of this process. In the lesson, the student is an active worker, he remembers the knowledge he acquired during the entire training process, partially applies it in new conditions, performs the methods of mental activity, moves from the known to the unknown. The essence of the new educational technology is to teach the student to think independently, to arouse interest and need for learning, to make him feel the pleasure of discovery. The word technology is Greek, techne - skill, art; logos means the meaning of doctrine. This word means a set of methods and methods used in the production process to obtain a finished product in industry or agriculture. In relation to the educational process, this concept requires the mutual coherence of reading and teaching, the separation of the stages of communication, the coordination of work to achieve the set goal in the educational process, ensuring their sequence and step-by-step, and the requirement of all planned work and actions. means to perform at the level of In other words, the concept of educational technology represents the art of teaching, the skill of teaching. The term "new educational technology" means using the art of education, organizing it efficiently, raising it to the level of world standards. Redagogical technology in education is to make students interested in teaching and to achieve full mastery of knowledge, to create an opportunity for students to express their opinion. The most important requirement for teaching in the process of redagogical technology is providing knowledge based on students' life experience, previously acquired knowledge and interests. A number of teaching methods are discussed in the literature and articles devoted to new educational technologies. These methods are presented as innovative methods. We will talk about some of these methods that can be used in music culture classes.

1. Modular educational technology . It is held in order to develop students' skills of independent work with textbooks, popular scientific and additional literature, creative and independent thinking. A unique feature of the modular education technology is the creation of a

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modular program that allows students to work independently and creatively on the subject being studied.

2. Cooperative learning technology . Its main idea is not only to complete educational tasks together, but also to teach students to study cooperatively, to create cooperation, mutual support and exchange of ideas between them.

3. Problem-based educational technology . It is to create a problem situation, ask questions, propose issues and problems, organize a discussion aimed at solving a problem situation, and confirm the correctness of conclusions.

4. Interactive method technology . Relying on the creativity of students, creating an environment of free discussion in the lesson. For this, they are divided into small groups and work with these groups during the lesson.

5. Technology of didactic games . Use of various didactic games during the lesson and use them to enliven the lesson, stimulate active movement and interest.

6. Test lessons . These are classes held with the purpose of testing certain knowledge and skills of students, and they are conducted by means of test sheets or checklists.

As a result of the expansion of the content, goals and tasks of education and training over time, its forms and methods are also improving. Currently, the main directions of human activity are turning into integrated systems, i.e. technologies, which enable the full realization of the intended goals. In the same way, in recent years, editorial technology has started to be used in the field of education. The concept of redagogical technology is a wide-ranging concept that has its place in the sciences of pedagogy and psychology. In educational technology, unlike various technologies in production, the material processed is the mental, spiritual, and moral qualities of the student (learner), which are influenced by teachers and educators in order to achieve certain goals. The concept of educational technology first appeared in the United States in the middle of the 20th century, and until the mid-1940s and 1950s, it was called "Educational technology" and this phrase was applied to teaching using technical tools. In the 1950s and 1960s, programmed education was considered, and in the 1970s, the term "pedagogical technology" was used to denote an educational process that guarantees the achievement of pre-planned and clearly defined goals. In 1979, the American Association of Educational Communications and Technologies defined educational technology as a complex, integrative process, and since the beginning of the 80s, educational computer and information technology has been called educational technology. Currently, this concept is given the following different definitions:

Technology - a set of methods, ways used in a work, art, skill. (Explanatory dictionary).

Technology - processing, the art of changing the situation, skill, ability is a set of methods. (VMSherel).

Redagogical technology - This is the process of influencing students (students) in certain conditions and sequences with the help of teaching (educational) tools of the teacher (educator) and forming predetermined personal qualities in them as a product of this activity. (*N. Saidakhmedov*).

Educational technology - a set of psychological procedures (settings) that determine the forms, methods, methods, ways of teaching and education, a special collection and arrangement (location) of educational tools; it consists of organizational and methodological tools of the redagogical process (BTLikhachev).

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Redagogical technology is a systematic method of creation, application and determination of all processes of teaching and knowledge acquisition, with the task of increasing educational forms, taking into account technical resources, people and their interaction. (UNESCO).

Redagogical technology is a unique new (innovative) approach to teaching. It is an expression of social-engineering thinking in pedagogy, an image of technocratic scientific consciousness transferred to the field of pedagogy, a certain standardization of the educational process. (BLFarberman)

Based on what has been said, we can give the following shortest and generalized definition of pedagogical technology:

" **Edagogical technology** is the activity of forming a perfect person".

At the same time, taking into account that the pedagogical technology is a wide-ranging, diverse concept, we can give a few more definitions of it below.

Redagogical technology is the process of teaching to create new information by mastering information, using it in practice, discovering new meanings in them and various connections between information.

Redagogical technology is a systematic method of creating, applying and determining the entire process of teaching and acquiring knowledge, taking into account technical resources and human interaction, which sets itself the task of optimizing educational forms.

With the achievement of national independence, our future paths, national idea and ideology were clearly defined. We have defined our educational goals and objectives and programs for their implementation.

Our president Sh. Mirziyoyev in a number of works on bringing up a morally and ideologically perfect generation has repeatedly emphasized that state policy in this direction is a priority issue. The ancient dreams, national and universal values, spiritual monuments of our ancestors are the basis for the formation of the goals and tasks of modern pedagogy. This goal is highlighted in the "National Personnel Training Program" adopted by our state. After all, the main goal of modern pedagogy is to train mature, highly qualified, spiritual, enlightened, independent thinking, competitive personnel.

Music affects the individual and the wider community alike (emotional, creative, aesthetic, ideological, educational, physiological, etc.). The teacher of music culture should always keep this in mind and conduct lessons at the expense of forming one characteristic, without crossing the limits of another. As we all know, before singing a song, tuning exercises are done. This is the main goal of forming vocal-choir skills - to strengthen the voice range and expand the voice range, as well as to develop the skills of singing, while preserving the natural features of the students' voices, lightness, sweetness and sonority. Vocal-choir skills are gradually prepared for singing based on the simple-to-complex principle:

- Even the simplest exercises should be sung in solfeggio, because the pitch is saved in the students' memory by the name of the notes.

- It is advisable to start vocal-choir exercises with mid-tone sol or sounds in the working diatonic, mi, fa, sol, because students cannot sing in pure intonation in bass or high tones.

- Carrying out the exercises with the help of visual aids (charts, notes on the board, cards, pictures) and having them performed by the teacher will increase the attention, memory and listening abilities of the students.

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-Students gradually develop the skills of singing in two voices. This forms their harmonic hearing, lad-tonal intuition.

- Use of various didactic games, rebuses, tarishmaq (stringing the omitted note) in the course of conducting vocal-choir exercises.

By applying such vocal-choir principles, students will develop the skills of harmonious and fluent singing in pure unison. The following vocal-choir exercises are used:

- Pure unison formation exercises
- Voice development exercises
- Articulation arrarat development exercises
- Wide breathing exercises
- Exercises to develop the skills of singing in two voices

It is very important to use various exercises to develop vocal-choir skills in students. Because it is with the help of vocal and choral skills that students' voices can be trained to be pleasant and sonorous.

Vocal-choir skills are divided into six types:

- Singing mode.
- Breath of anger.
- Sound generation.
- Setup.
- Ensemble.
- Pronunciation.

During exercises or singing songs, students should be taught to breathe according to the teacher's hand gestures and to save it, start and end at the same time . It is also important to pay attention to singing in a soft and gentle vocal voice without shouting. Theatrologist scientist M. Rahmonov writes, "In the early stages of human history, music appeared on the scene in an inextricable connection with the art of rantomime and dance. It was an integral part of the life and work of people of the primitive society living in the territory of Uzbekistan. The earliest songs in primitive times would have been very simple. "Hunting game" and "music" and "songs" that led rantomim dance games in various ceremonies consisted mainly of melodies and recitatives repeating words and sounds over and over again. The basis of the choir team is the work of the vocal choir in it. Vocal-choir complex work lays the foundation for the successful work of the choir. The quality of vocal work in the choir depends on the qualifications of the choir conductor, vocal ability and editing skills. The goal of vocal work in the choir is to develop proper singing skills in singers. For vocal work:

- working on the important elements of the choir (achieving harmony, good words, pronunciation, artistic means of expression);
- proper breathing, vocal sound barro and its formation;
- such as making the members of the choir have the same vocal skills. Barro important elements of choral performance depends on its vocal and choral technique.

Vocal-choir technique mainly includes breathing, sound generation, stretching, dynamics, intonation and diction skills. If the choir collective does not have good vocal technique, it will not have harmony (ensemble), clear music, clear pronunciation and artistic expression in the performance of the choir. Therefore, it is always necessary to develop and improve vocal choir techniques in the choir .

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